

ANALYSIS OF NEW ROUTES IN INTERNATIONAL SHIPPING

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Abstract: The field of international shipping today attracts a lot of attention and interest for countries and companies in the world. Developing, proposing, and identifying challenges and opportunities for new shipping routes is the focus of scientific research in this field. The article briefly describes topics such as modern issues of international cargo transportation, the importance of defining new routes and finding solutions to them, development of international transportation systems, optimization of logistics processes, and further development of international trade activities.

Keywords: Corridors, traffic, vehicle, transportation, security, problem, solution, network, problem, solution, Mazar-e-Sharif, Bandar Abbas (route of Iran, People's Republic of China, Lianyungang, Far East Russian port Nakhodka, via Khorgos Through the Chinese border, TRASEKA, Brest (Belarus), Klaipeda (Lithuania, Il'ichevsk (Ukraine).

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev said at a meeting dedicated to reforms in the transport sector in the country: "This sector is the lifeblood of the economy. If we do not take transport and logistics to a new level, we will not be able to ensure the stable development of the economy," he emphasized. It also defined tasks such as the expansion of the modern road network for international transit cargo and the expansion of the international transit road network in the direction of rail transport.[1]

The transport system is one of the necessary factors for the effective functioning of the country's economy, and it is the most important infrastructure for sustainable growth.

In modern conditions, when the economies of countries are interconnected, the development of transport and communication systems that work effectively in the world production network is a necessary condition for countries to enter this global network. Uzbekistan is one of the largest countries of Central Asia, and international transport corridors pass through its territory. Uzbekistan is a very convenient and important region for Europe-Asia transits.

The rapid development of foreign economic trade in the Republic of Uzbekistan requires the organization of efficient international cargo transportation. The share of the public transport complex in the gross domestic product of the Republic of Uzbekistan is about 8.0%, while the number of people employed in this sector is 3.8%. In 2022, the freight turnover by all types of transport was 75185.4 million ton-

kilometers, which increased by 5% compared to 2021. The volume of cargo transportation within the republic is 1346 million tons. Car transport takes the leading place in domestic cargo transportation with 93%. According to the analysis of the last five years, a steady growth rate of international cargo transportation is observed in Uzbekistan. [2]

Analysis of the dynamics of export cargo transportation in 2021-2022 shows variable growth and a decrease in volumes. During this period, the volume of transportation of imported goods increased. The development of international transportation of goods and passengers indicates the stability of establishing economic relations with many countries near and far abroad. It is necessary to develop transport corridors for effective implementation of international transport[3].

International transport corridor (transport corridor, MTK) is a high-tech transport system that concentrates public surface transport (railway, road, river) and telecommunications in common directions. The concept of "corridor" generally includes all types of transportation: roads, sea, river, railway and air sections, main pipelines, sea, river and air ports, railway stations and multimodal terminals. includes. The international transport corridor serves to develop and improve international relations in cargo and passenger transport. Transport corridors are strong polymer highways that meet the requirements of international standards operating on the basis of uniform technological, organizational, legal norms and rules, which make it possible to significantly reduce the duration and cost of transportation, increase their quality and reliability.[4]

In solving transport problems related to ensuring interstate economic, cultural and other relations, expanding international cooperation and deepening the integration processes of the formation of international transport corridors, as well as international transport with agreed technical parameters and ensuring the use of joint transport technologies the expediency of creating the transport infrastructure, the transport system plays a leading role as the basis for the integration of the national transport system into the global transport system.[5]

The UN expert group adopted the following definition of an International Transport Corridor: "it is a part of a national or international transport system that provides important international freight and passenger transport between separate geographical areas, operating in this direction includes rolling stock and stationary devices of all types of transport, as well as technological, organizational and legal conditions of transport".

1) problems of the development of transport corridors have the following characteristics: transport corridors should be considered not only from the point of view of integration into the international economic transport system, but also as the most important element of the world logistics system;

2) increased competition in the transport services market;

3) attraction of transit cargo;

4) the role of seaports in attracting transit cargo;

5) change the structure and direction of regional cargo flows;

6) increasing attention to the development of the transport system;

7) strengthening the role of the political factor in the operation of transport corridors.

Transport corridors are part of the international transport infrastructure. In this regard, their

activities are subject to the requirements specified in international documents and agreements. The main ones are: - Common Transport Policy (OTP) adopted by the Prague Declaration of 1991; - White Paper of the European Union; - Green Book of the European Union; - materials of the sub-committee of the International Union of Railways; - European Agreement on International Main Railway Lines; - European agreement on the most important routes of international combined transport and other documents. International transport corridors are the main element of international logistics systems, within which technological and technical systems in the field of goods delivery are combined. These include: limited loads and lengths of wagons, cars, containers, pallets; capacity of railways and roads.

The following issues are resolved during the construction of international logistics systems: - creation of a free transportation market; - use of "floating" tariffs; - development of rules for the development and protection of the common market of logistics processes; - liberalization of transport and customs procedures; - coordinating the carrying capacity of highway transport and the operation of railway storage facilities; - implementation of international rules, forms and standards that are mandatory for members of society. Integration of transport links of countries, creation of an effective and unified transport infrastructure in each of them with sufficient capacity to serve international freight and passenger transport on a regional scale.[6]

EYEC of the United Nations Organization is carrying out effective work on the creation of the Single European infrastructure, in particular: - the European highway network; - European railway network; European inland waterways system.

The Republic of Uzbekistan has an important geostrategic position in the Central Asian region, which ensures the development of an important transport and communication complex and its effective integration into the international transit system.[7]

Existing corridors in the field of railway transport

At present, delivery of Uzbekistan's export goods to international markets is carried out through 9 major railway corridors

1. Afghanistan (Mazari-Sharif), Ghalaba (Surkhandarya region) through the inter-governmental connection point. The total distance is 933 km, of which 858 km - Tashkent - Galaba - in the territory of Uzbekistan, 75 km - in the territory of Afghanistan - Khairaton - Mazori Sharif. The average transport time is 4 days.

2. Bandar Abbas (Iran) transit through Turkmenistan and Persian Gulf (Jebel Ali (UAE), Sohar (Oman), South (Karachi, Pakistan), Mumbai (India), Chittagong (Bangladesh) East Asia (Thailand, Malaysia, Indonesia, Vietnam)

The route is located in Turkmenistan and the Islamic Republic of Iran. Route distance - 2827 km, average delivery time - 13 days (Bandar Abbas).

The transport corridor through the port of Bandar Abbas is the most economically efficient and the cheapest.

3. The direction of the People's Republic of China. Lianyungang (PRC) through the Intergovernmental Friendship Point (Republic of Kazakhstan) The route passes through the territories of the Republic of Kazakhstan and the People's Republic of China. Distance - 5908 km, average delivery time 14 days

4. Far East Russian port Nakhodka route The route crosses the territory of the Republic of Kazakhstan and the Russian Federation. The distance is 8683 km, the average delivery time is 22 days.

5. South-East Asian countries and Eastern ports of China, through Kazakhstan - through the Chinese border through Altinkol / Khorgos. The route passes through the territory of the Republic of Kazakhstan and the People's Republic of China. Length - 1292 to Khorgos, delivery time - 13 days. The

distance to Lianyungang is 4900 km. The route is used for multimodal transport (containers).

6. TRASEKA (transit through Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan and Azerbaijan) Transcaucasian corridor to the Black Sea Ports of Poti and Batumi.

The route crosses the territories of Turkmenistan, the Caspian Sea, the Republic of Azerbaijan and Georgia. Distance - 2667 km (Poti), average delivery time 14 days

7. To the countries of the European Union (in transit to Kazakhstan and Russia) through the border points of Chop (Ukraine) and Brest (Belarus). Brest (Belarus) interstate junction. The route passes through the territory of Kazakhstan, the Russian Federation and Belarus. Distance - 4385 km, average delivery time - 14 days. Print Interstate Junction (Ukraine). The route passes through the territories of Kazakhstan, the Russian Federation and Ukraine. Distance - 4779 km, average delivery time - 18 days

8. Transit through the Baltic ports to Klaipėda (Lithuania), Riga, Liepaja and Ventspils (Latvia), Tallinn (Estonia) and St. Petersburg port (Russian Federation) through Kazakhstan and Russia. The route passes through the territories of Kazakhstan and the Russian Federation. Distance - 4263 km, average delivery time - 14 days.[8]

Port of Tallinn (Estonia). The route passes through the territories of Kazakhstan and the Russian Federation. Distance - 4505 km, average delivery time - 15 days.

Port of Riga (Latvia). The route passes through the territories of Kazakhstan and the Russian Federation. Distance - 4348 km, average delivery time - 14 days

Port of Klaipėda (Lithuania) The route passes through the territories of Kazakhstan, the Russian Federation and Latvia. Distance - 4603 km, average delivery time - 16 days [9].

9. Passing through Kazakhstan and Russia to the ports of Ilyichevsk (Ukraine) and Novorossiysk (Russia), Port of Ilyichevsk (Ukraine) The route passes through the territories of Kazakhstan, the Russian Federation and Latvia. Distance - 4239 km, average delivery time - 15 days.

I. Janub, Janubiy – G'arbiy yo'nalish			
«Termez – Mazari Sharif»	85	1 kun	1200
«Toshkent – Buxoro – Turkmanobod – Mari – Saraxs – Bandar–Abbos»	3 065	6-7 kun (48/48 soat)	2 400-2 600
«Toshkent – Buxoro – Turkmanobod – Mari – Saraxs – Mersin»	4 208	12-14 kun (48/48 soat)	3 000-3 300
«Toshkent – Buxoro – Turkmanobod – Mari – Saraxs – Istanbul – Sofiya»	5 156	14-15 kun (48/48 soat)	4 000-4 300
II. Shimoliy, Shimoliy–G'arbiy yo'nalish			
«Toshkent – Qo'ng'iro't – Beyneu – Saratov – Moskva –Riga (Vilnyus)»	4 781 (Riga) 4 857 (Vilnyus)	10-14 kun (48/48 soat)	2 000-2 300
«Toshkent – Qo'ng'iro't – Beyneu – Saratov – Moskva – Smolensk – Brest – (Polsha, Germaniya, Fransiya, Ispaniya va boshqalar)»	4 421 (Minsk) 4 800 (Varshava) 5 400 (Berlin) 6 493 (Amsterdam) 6 842 (Parij) 8 117 (Madrid)	9-10 kun 10-12 kun 13-15 kun 14-16 kun 15-17 kun 17-19 kun (48/48 soat)	2 200-2 400 (Minsk) 2 300-2 500 (Varshava) 3 100-3 400 (Berlin)
«Toshkent – Qo'ng'iro't – Beyneu – Astraxan – Volgograd – Kiyev – (Polsha, Chexiya, Avstriya Slovakiya va boshqalar)»	4 140 (Kiyev) 5 400 (Praga) 5 400 (Vena) 5 400 (Bratislava)	9-10 kun 13-15 kun 13-15 kun 13-15 kun (48/48 soat)	2 200-2 500 (Kiyev) 3 000-3 300
«Toshkent – Qo'ng'iro't – Beyneu – Astraxan – Tbilisi – Batumi – Trabzon –Samsun – Istanbul – (Bolgariya, Ruminiya)»	5 500 (Sofiya) 5 600 (Buxarest)	14-15 kun 14-15 kun (48/48 soat)	4 000-4 300
III. G'arbiy yo'nalish			
«Toshkent – Qo'ng'iro't – Beyneu – Oqtau – Boku – Tbilisi – Poti – (Bolgariya, Ruminiya va boshqalar)»	4 558 (Konstansa) 4 645 (Burgas)	19-21 kun	4 500-4 700
«Toshkent – Buxoro – Turkmanobod– Mari – Turkmanboshi – Boku – Tbilisi – Poti – (Bolgariya, Ruminiya, Vengriya va boshqalar)»	4 320 (Burgas) 4 233 (Konstansa)	19-21 kun	4 700-4 900

current issues and priority areas of development of international road transport between countries along the corridors, in particular, general approaches to solving the issue related to the digitalization of document exchange in the process of international cargo transportation, the lack of professional personnel (primarily qualified drivers) are discussing the advantages and disadvantages of development, prospective transport corridors and routes, aspects related to the formation of multilateral cooperation necessary for their successful development.[10]

To strengthen mutual cooperation between the participants of international road transport in the main directions of the national car carriers of Uzbekistan, to discuss the main current issues in the course of international cargo transportation in Eurasia and the European Union, to increase the transport and transit potential of Uzbekistan. In order to widely promote the work being carried out, the Ministry of Transport, in cooperation with the International Road Transport Union and the International Association of Truckers of Uzbekistan, organized an international conference on "International road transport: problems and opportunities".

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